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ABSTRACT

Digitalisation in agriculture has accelerated through the adoption of sensors, platforms, and data-driven technologies, promising enhanced efficiency, traceability, and sustainability. However, in the UK beef sector, these anticipated benefits have not been fully realised. This paper argues that the primary constraint is not the absence of data or technological capability, but the fragmentation, lack of interoperability, and limited transparency of existing data infrastructures. Drawing on interdisciplinary literature and sectoral insights, including evidence from the BeefTwin project, we demonstrate that current systems remain largely compliance-oriented and fail to support advanced analytics or ecosystem-level coordination. We reposition digital transformation in this context as a data governance challenge, emphasising the need for integrated architectures, shared standards, and collaborative governance mechanisms. This perspective contributes to the literature by shifting the focus from tool adoption to systemic data integration as a prerequisite for meaningful digital transformation.

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Beyond Smart Farming Tools: Data Governance and the Limits of Digitalisation in UK Beef Production

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Abstract

Digitalisation in agriculture has accelerated through the adoption of sensors, platforms, and data-driven technologies, promising enhanced efficiency, traceability, and sustainability. However, in the UK beef sector, these anticipated benefits have not been fully realised. This paper argues that the primary constraint is not the absence of data or technological capability, but the fragmentation, lack of interoperability, and limited transparency of existing data infrastructures. Drawing on interdisciplinary literature and sectoral insights, including evidence from the BeefTwin project, we demonstrate that current systems remain largely compliance-oriented and fail to support advanced analytics or ecosystem-level coordination. We reposition digital transformation in this context as a data governance challenge, emphasising the need for integrated architectures, shared standards, and collaborative governance mechanisms. This perspective contributes to the literature by shifting the focus from tool adoption to systemic data integration as a prerequisite for meaningful digital transformation.

Key words: Digital Transformation, Data Governance, Data Interoperability, Traceability, Beef Supply Chain

1. Introduction

Digital transformation has become a central theme in contemporary agricultural systems, with increasing emphasis on the role of digital technologies in improving productivity, sustainability, and supply chain coordination (Papadopoulos et al., 2025). In livestock sectors, including beef production, a wide range of digital tools—such as sensors, farm management platforms, and traceability systems—have been introduced to enhance monitoring and decision-making processes.

Despite these advancements, the UK beef sector presents a paradoxical situation. While substantial volumes of data are generated across the value chain, the sector has yet to realise the transformative potential associated with digitalisation. This suggests that the challenge lies not in data generation per se, but in the structural limitations of how data is managed, shared, and utilised.

Existing research often frames digital transformation as a technology adoption problem (Fielke et al., 2020; Ayre et al., 2019). However, such perspectives overlook the systemic and relational dimensions of data use, particularly in fragmented and multi-actor environments such as agricultural supply chains. This paper therefore argues that the key barriers to digital transformation in UK beef production are rooted in data governance, specifically the lack of interoperability, transparency, and coordination across existing data systems.

2. Digitalisation in UK Beef Production

The UK beef sector has experienced increasing levels of digitalisation through the implementation of various data collection systems, including livestock identification, movement tracking, and farm-level management tools. These systems generate detailed datasets relating to animal health, welfare, feeding practices, and production performance.

However, these data are typically:

- distributed across multiple platforms,
- controlled by different stakeholders,
- and embedded within proprietary systems.

As a result, data flows remain fragmented and largely confined within organisational boundaries. This reflects a broader trend identified in agricultural digitalisation literature, where data infrastructures are often shaped by institutional and regulatory requirements rather than by considerations of interoperability or value creation (Bronson & Knezevic, 2016; Carolan, 2017).

Moreover, many of these systems are designed primarily to fulfil compliance obligations, such as traceability and assurance schemes. While these functions are essential, they do not inherently support advanced data use, such as predictive analytics or cross-system optimisation.

Figure 1 illustrates that digitalisation in the UK beef sector is shaped by the interaction of regulatory requirements, technological capability, economic pressures, and sustainability and societal expectations, while also highlighting the structural disconnect between these drivers.

Figure1. Key drivers of digitalisation in the UK beef sector and the structural gaps limiting data integration and effective use of advanced digital technologies

3. Traceability, Transparency, and Data Limitations

Traceability is frequently cited as a key benefit of digitalisation in agriculture. In the UK beef sector, systems such as cattle identification and movement tracking provide a foundation for traceability. However, full end-to-end transparency remains limited.

This limitation arises from several interrelated factors:

- Data fragmentation across multiple systems
- Inconsistent data standards and formats
- Restricted data access due to ownership and commercial concerns
- Limited integration across different stages of the value chain

Consequently, while data exists at various points, it cannot be easily combined to produce a comprehensive and reliable view of the system. This undermines the ability to verify claims related to sustainability, animal welfare, and product quality.

As highlighted in previous studies, transparency in agri-food systems is not solely a function of data availability, but of data accessibility and interoperability (Rotz et al., 2019; Kamilaris et al., 2017). In this context, the UK beef sector remains constrained by structural barriers that limit the effective use of existing data resources.

Table 1. Core data parameters currently collected across the UK beef supply chain and their role in enabling digitalisation, analytics, and advanced smart farming capabilities

Thematic Domain	Data Parameter Category	Examples of Parameters	Current Use in UK Beef Farming	Utility for Digitalisation and Governance	Enabled Advanced Capabilities	Digital Value Creation Pathway	Reference
Identity & Traceability Foundations	Animal Identity and Lineage	Ear tag number, EID, breed, sex, date of birth, parentage	Mandatory statutory registration via BCMS; fragmented across systems	Persistent digital identity enabling lifecycle linkage; foundational for auditability	Lifecycle analytics, digital twins (DTs), traceability assurance	Enables whole-lifecycle benchmarking; strengthens provenance claims and consumer trust	Defra (2023); Groher et al. (2020); Losacco et al. (2025)
	Movement and Location (CPH & SBI)	County Parish Holding (CPH) codes, Single Business Identifier (SBI), movement dates, transport events	Reported for statutory traceability; business- and holding-level data often siloed	Enables spatial-temporal integration; supports biosecurity and regulatory governance	Disease modelling, exposure mapping, provenance verification	Reduces biosecurity risk; enables location-based sustainability accounting; strengthens supply chain assurance	Defra (2023); Schillings et al. (2022)
Animal Health & Welfare Monitoring	Health and Veterinary Records	Treatments, medicines, dosage, withdrawal	Recorded in farm software or private platforms;	Supports predictive health analytics;	AI-driven disease detection;	Reduces mortality and input costs; supports	Groher et al. (2020); Losacco

Thematic Domain	Data Parameter Category	Examples of Parameters	Current Use in UK Beef Farming	Utility for Digitalisation and Governance	Enabled Advanced Capabilities	Digital Value Creation Pathway	Reference
Production & Environmental Performance	Welfare Indicators	Lameness scores, body condition scores, mortality, housing conditions	Periodic recording for assurance audits	Makes ethical dimensions visible; supports accountability and oversight	Real-time welfare monitoring; automated assurance systems	Enhances retailer compliance; strengthens societal legitimacy and brand value	Brown-Brandl (2025); Manning et al. (2023)
	Feeding and Nutrition	Feed type, origin, ration composition, grazing allocation	Often recorded separately or informally	Links management decisions to productivity and emissions; supports sustainability governance	Feed optimisation; carbon footprint modelling	Improves margin efficiency; reduces feed waste and environmental intensity	Groher et al. (2020); Arulmozhi et al. (2024)
	Environmental Parameters	Fertiliser use, pasture management, housing environment, manure handling	Increasingly required but inconsistently structured	Enables environmental reporting and compliance; central to governance of sustainability claims	Emissions modelling; environmental compliance analytics	Enables product-level GHG reporting; access to sustainability premiums and green finance	UK Parliament POST (2024); Manning et al. (2023)
Long-Term Optimisation & Market Feedback	Performance and Growth	Live weight, daily live-weight gain (DLWG), feed efficiency	Collected intermittently; rarely integrated across lifecycle	Core predictive analytics data; supports benchmarking governance	Finishing-time prediction; productivity optimisation	Improves production planning; reduces cost variability; enhances profitability	Losacco et al. (2025); Schillings et al. (2022)
	Genetic and Genomic Data	Estimated Breeding Values (EBVs), genomic markers, breeding indices	Available through breeding programmes; weak linkage to lifetime data	Supports long-term optimisation; requires governance on consent and reuse	Data-driven breeding strategies	Long-term productivity gains; resilience to climate and disease pressures	Groher et al. (2020); Losacco et al. (2025)
	Slaughter and Carcass Outcomes	Carcass weight, EUROP	Captured at abattoirs; limited	Closes lifecycle learning	Market alignment; continuous	Aligns farm output with processor	Manning (2025); Schillings

Thematic Domain	Data Parameter Category	Examples of Parameters	Current Use in UK Beef Farming	Utility for Digitalisation and Governance	Enabled Advanced Capabilities	Digital Value Creation Pathway	Reference
		conformation grade, fat class, yields	feedback to farms	loop; enables cross-chain accountability	improvement analytics	demand; improves price realisation and market competitiveness	et al. (2022)

4. Interoperability and Fragmented Data Ecosystems

Interoperability is widely recognised as a critical enabler of digital transformation (Janssen et al., 2020). However, in the UK beef sector, interoperability remains limited due to the absence of shared data standards and integration frameworks.

Current data systems operate largely in isolation, resulting in:

- duplication of data entry,
- inconsistencies in data quality,
- and inefficiencies in information exchange.

These challenges are exacerbated by the presence of proprietary platforms, which restrict data sharing and create barriers to collaboration. As a result, the sector lacks a unified data ecosystem capable of supporting coordinated decision-making.

The absence of interoperability not only limits operational efficiency but also constrains the development of more advanced digital applications, such as artificial intelligence and digital twins. Without integrated datasets, these technologies cannot be effectively deployed at scale.

5. The Limitations of Tool-Centric Approaches

Much of the current discourse on agricultural digitalisation focuses on the adoption of new tools and technologies. While these tools can enhance specific aspects of farm management, they often fail to address underlying structural issues related to data fragmentation and governance.

This has led to a situation where digitalisation efforts are incremental rather than transformative. Technologies are layered onto existing systems without fundamentally altering how data is organised or utilised.

As noted by Klerkx et al. (2019), digital agriculture initiatives frequently underestimate the importance of institutional and organisational factors. In the case of UK beef production, the continued emphasis on tool adoption risks reinforcing existing inefficiencies rather than resolving them.

6. Reframing Digital Transformation as a Data Governance Challenge

This paper proposes a shift in perspective, from viewing digital transformation as a technological issue to understanding it as a data governance challenge.

Data governance encompasses the rules, standards, and practices that determine how data is collected, shared, and used. In the UK beef sector, several governance gaps can be identified:

- Lack of standardised data formats
- Ambiguity around data ownership and access rights
- Limited mechanisms for cross-organisational coordination
- Weak incentives for data sharing

These gaps contribute to the persistence of fragmented data systems and inhibit the development of integrated digital infrastructures.

Addressing these challenges requires a move toward collaborative governance models, where stakeholders collectively establish standards and frameworks for data sharing. Such approaches have been highlighted as critical in other sectors undergoing digital transformation (Janssen et al., 2020).

7. Towards Integrated and Transparent Data Ecosystems

To unlock the full potential of digitalisation in UK beef production, a transition toward integrated and transparent data ecosystems is required.

This involves several key components:

Data Integration

Linking datasets across different stages of the value chain to enable holistic analysis.

Standardisation

Developing common data formats and protocols to facilitate interoperability.

Transparency

Enhancing visibility across stakeholders to build trust and improve coordination.

Governance

Establishing clear frameworks for data ownership, access, and use.

Such developments would enable the transition from compliance-driven data systems to value-driven data ecosystems, supporting advanced analytics and more effective decision-making.

8. Conclusion

This paper has argued that the limitations of digitalisation in UK beef production are not primarily technological, but structural. Despite the availability of substantial data, fragmentation, lack of interoperability, and limited transparency constrain its effective use. By reframing digital transformation as a data governance challenge, this study highlights the need for integrated, standardised, and collaboratively governed data systems. Without such changes, the sector is unlikely to realise the full benefits of digital technologies. Future research should explore governance models and institutional arrangements that can support this transition, as well as the role of policy in facilitating data integration across agricultural systems.

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